

SERIOUS CONSEQUENCES OF RISK-BASED GAMBLING

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Abstract: This article reviews psychological research on online gambling addiction in individuals with risk-taking. Also, risk-based games and their negative factors and effects on society, as well as the negative impact of these games on the human psyche, are described.

Keywords: totalizator, gambling addiction, virtual games, "1xbet", social isolation, depression, online casino, virtual world, mental health, stress, emotional reactivity, internet gambling anonymity, digital security, depression, anxiety, online gambling, self-control.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются психологические исследования зависимости от азартных игр в Интернете у людей, склонных к риску. Также описаны рискованные игры и их негативные факторы и влияние на общество, а также негативное влияние этих игр на психику человека.

Ключевые слова: тотализатор, азартная зависимость, виртуальные игры, «1xbet», социальная изоляция, депрессия, онлайн-казино, виртуальный мир, психическое здоровье, стресс, эмоциональная реактивность, анонимность азартных игр в Интернете, цифровая безопасность, депрессия, тревога, азартные игры в Интернете, самоконтроль.

Enter. There are many cases of people's desire to earn easy and fast money without working hard, dependence on technologies, switching between the real and virtual world. Those addicted to such games are wasting not only their time, but also millions of money. It is a pity that young people who have not yet learned the difference between good and bad are committing suicide because of huge debts. They still don't understand that the only way to win these games is not to play. If you pay attention, betting games and lotteries are rapidly becoming popular in countries with low living standards and low incomes. At a time when salaries are low and career growth paths seem narrow, a person will make some kind of "miraculous achievement". Dreaming leads people to correspond with a "foreign relative who left a large inheritance", network marketing spider web and financial pyramid. It is important to note that no one knows of those who have become rich by playing the totalizer, but, unfortunately, there are many among us who have lost their homes. If you pay attention, you can observe that the totalizator is becoming popular in Uzbekistan mainly among young people. Young people who are just entering the big life want to have instant success and achievements that will be achieved step by step throughout their life. In addition, if you pay attention, the countries where betting games and lotteries become popular are countries with low living standards and low incomes. This is caused by people's strong desire to fundamentally improve their lives through some "miraculous achievement".

Research methodology. Recently, the trend of betting on sports games has become more and more popular among young people. To some extent, this is caused by the strong

desire of some people to earn easy money without putting effort into work. As a result, the money, energy and time that should be spent on professional development and education are wasted on unnecessary and harmful "gambling". A bookmaker pretends to be an intermediary between gamblers, but in fact, he drags the player into the trap of "addict" and "milks" the poor person for a long time. Recently, online gambling has become an integral part of the life of certain categories of people. As a result of such games, there are many cases of falling into not only the financial impact, but also the emotional impact that causes addiction. It is one of the sad cases that illegal gambling, which is foreign to our national traditions and mentality, as well as our religious views, is popularized online and attracts teenagers and young people. There are even cases of people losing large amounts of money in such games and eventually committing suicide or committing a crime to pay for their lost money.

Research results. Those who try to earn money in the totalizator fall into the trap of the game, as if under the influence of drugs. According to data, more than 6 million people in the United States have reported that in recent years they have become ill, need treatment, and are unable to control themselves due to gambling. Most of those who become victims of such games based on risk on the Internet are representatives of generation "Z" (derived from the word *zumer*, which does not have internet literacy). This generation is growing up with mobile phones - those born between 1997 and 2015. In 2019, 97 percent of them used a mobile phone, and 78 percent of representatives of generation Z indicated smart devices as the main means of obtaining information and having fun.

Waste of time. Initially earning additional income, then falling into the "frenzy" and spending days, weeks, months and even years in order to compensate for the lost money, a person loses the priceless gift that he should invest for his personal development.

Effects on health. Games based on risk create a feeling of hopelessness and helplessness in a person. They suffer from depression, migraines, intestinal diseases and other stress-related problems. Losing a large amount of money destroys human well-being. Those who are addicted to the game, even when they are lying down or standing up, they always think about betting and winning. Due to its harmful consequences, gambling addiction is one of the most important health problems in many countries.

Financial problems. A person unjustifiably loses the funds that he should allocate to himself, his relatives and good deeds. Due to financial difficulties, delinquency and crimes increase among people.

In short, the illegal organization and conduct of gambling and other games based on risk today not only affects citizens psychologically, but also leads to financial dependence and family disputes. Also, this activity opens the way to the increase of non-bank circulation of cash, the evasion of paying taxes and other payments, and thereby harms the economic development of our country. Accordingly, increasing the awareness of citizens, strengthening the control of the state in this regard, and regular control by parents over the productive use of their children's free time serves to prevent the above negative evils.

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